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2.3. provide Licensees with the author data pulled from OA Intelligence that is sent to OA Switchboard, in Excel format, during the third quarter of the year (between June-August) depending on schedule, including author affiliation at acceptance date, to collaborate with the Licensees on a pilot to provide a bi-annual report which allows the identification of articles published OA by corresponding authors affiliated with Licensees under this agreement; ASM will also supply aggregated subscriber spend, which cannot include member discount amounts.

2.4. host information relating to the OA publishing opportunities it offers on the website - <https://journals.asm.org/s2o>:

2.5 enable Retroactive Open Access Publishing: if authors or institutions bring to ASM's attention articles that should be published Open Access, such as in the case of an author not properly choosing the correct affiliated institution, or ASM not properly matching an institution to their subscriber base, ASM shall retroactively make the article Open Access and make a refund if it is determined that paying corresponding author is from a subscribing institution.

AMENDMENT 1

2026 ASM S2O Flat Fee Pilot Option

The American Society for Microbiology has introduced an option, called the Subscribe to Open (S2O) Flat Fee Pilot, to ZB Med members that offers unlimited publishing for the 2026 Subscription Year in any of the subscribed S2O titles. Like the standard S2O Subscription Model, this model offers read access to all titles within the All-Inclusive Package:

All-Inclusive Package Subscription Journals

- Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy **(S2O)**
- Applied and Environmental Microbiology **(S2O)**
- Clinical Microbiology Reviews
- Infection and Immunity **(S2O)**
- Journal of Bacteriology **(S2O)**
- Journal of Clinical Microbiology **(S2O)**
- Journal of Virology **(S2O)**
- Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews

Open Access journals:

- Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education
- mBio
- Microbiology Resource Announcements
- Microbiology Spectrum
- mSphere
- mSystems
- ASM Case Reports
- ASM Animal Microbiology
- ASM Food Microbiology

The Flat Fee Model also offers a Publication component, in which authors from subscribing institutions may publish in any of the journals labeled “S2O” above. These articles will be made Open Access immediately upon publication.

The cost for each institution is a combination of their S2O Subscription Fee, plus a Publication Fee based on previous publication history from 2023 to 2025. Therefore, amounts vary by institution.

The fixed price increase for 2026, 2027, and 2028 is 2.5% each year.

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